

Optimizing Revenue and Room Occupancy Strategies in 3-5 Star Hotels in Ghana: A Mixed Methods Approach

¹John Adanse*, ²Rosemarie Khayiya (PhD), ³Vincent Maranga (PhD)

¹School of Business, Economics and Tourism Management, Department of Hospitality Management, Kenyatta University, Nairobi, Kenya & School of Applied Science and Arts, Department of Hotel, Catering and Institutional Management, Bolgatanga Technical University, Box 767, Bolgatanga, Upper East Region, Ghana

Corresponding author: johnadanse@bolgatu.edu.gh; Orcid ID: [0000-0003-0582-6613](https://orcid.org/0000-0003-0582-6613)

²School of Business, Economics and Tourism Management, Department of Hospitality Management, Kenyatta University, Nairobi, Kenya
khayiya.rosemarie@ku.ac.ke; Orchid ID: [000-0002-1567-3377](https://orcid.org/000-0002-1567-3377)

³School of Business, Economics and Tourism Management, Department of Hospitality Management, Kenyatta University, Nairobi, Kenya
maranga.vincent@ku.ac.ke; Orchid ID: [0000-0002-1927-5966](https://orcid.org/0000-0002-1927-5966)

Abstract

Generating adequate income to sustain business activities is essential for an organization's profitability. Implementing strategies to maximize revenue is critical for obtaining necessary resources and ensuring ongoing success. This study examined the strategies utilized by 3-5 star-rated hotels in selected regions of Ghana to achieve optimal room occupancy and maximize revenue during periods of low demand. A descriptive survey with a mixed-methods approach was conducted, guided by profit maximization theory. A sample size of 60 3-5 star-rated hotels was determined using the Yamane (1967) formula and stratified random sampling. Data collection involved questionnaires and key informant interviews with 60 managers, 420 department heads, and 16 key informants from the selected hotels. Quantitative data were collected through questionnaires, while qualitative data were obtained from key informant interviews. A multiple linear regression model was employed to analyze the data, with results presented in tables and charts. The findings showed a strong correlation (over 82%) between the strategies used and room occupancy rates. It is recommended that 3-5 star hotels in Ghana continue to offer special rates and targeted marketing efforts, and collaborate with relevant parties to broaden their reach and attract more guests.

Keywords: Revenue Maximization, Room Occupancy, Hotel Strategies, Profit Maximization Theory, Ghana Hospitality

Introduction

The hotel business falls under the hospitality industry, and it deals with the provision of food and accommodation. It was established that the hotel industry is on a growing trend, and it was projected that by 2019, it would generate about 1.47 trillion United

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States dollars globally (Lock, 2021). In Ghana, hotels together with travel agencies contributed 3% towards gross domestic product (GDP) at the national level in 2016, which was equal to 4.9 million Ghanaian cedi (GHC) or USD 1.2 million (Ansah, 2019). The earnings from the sector are expected to increase by 5.6% in 2017 and 5.1% in 2027, thus projecting GDP contributions of GHC 5.2 million (USD 1.2 million) and GHC 8.6 million (USD 2 million), respectively (Ansah, 2019). Despite the challenges presented by the COVID-19 pandemic, the hotel industry in Ghana continues to exhibit signs of growth and potential in the future. This can be attributed to government policies aimed at increasing hotel occupancy (Danso et al., 2020).

In any business, the goal for revenue maximisation is to implement management techniques that will cause the highest number of sales of services and products (Tyburski, 2016). These include creating a demand for goods in the short run at favourable prices, thus increasing total income from their sales (Nagle & Müller, 2017). Initially applied by Marriott International Hotels in the 1980s, it involves forecasting demand and providing capacity recommendations for different scenarios within the hospitality industry (Abrate et al., 2019). The hotel industry, since the year 1980, has been widely known for implementing revenue maximisation concepts to resolve the problem of fixed high costs and capacity constraints in service delivery encountered by the sector in the 21st century (Hao, Xiao, & Chon 2020; Rodríguez-Algeciras & Talon-Ballester, 2017; Dileep & Mathew, 2017).

Research, like the Majorca study by Vives, Jacob, and Payeras (2018), highlights how crucial it is to raise hotel occupancy in order to boost revenue. Research from both domestic and international sources, with an emphasis on pricing strategies, revenue forecasting, price optimisation, and technology, shows the link between strategic management responses and revenue maximisation (Vives et al., 2018; Abrate et al., 2019; Teemu, 2020). Hotels that are struggling with revenue loss frequently cut prices in an effort to draw guests and boost room occupancy.

For a hotel manager, low occupancy or unoccupied rooms are the greatest nightmare. In order to ensure maximum revenue collection, it is imperative to maintain optimum hotel bed occupancy (Vives, Jacob, & Payeras, 2018). Many factors contribute to low hotel bed occupancy, including excessive costs, bad-quality rooms, low season or slow periods, and poor marketing (lack of visibility). Hotels use a variety of tactics to guarantee bed occupancy. In order to guarantee bed occupancy, hotels employ various strategies such as group sales, direct sales, destination marketing, cross-promotion, revenue management sales, guest rewards sales strategy, re-marketing, and creating a comfortable environment for guests (Site Miinder, 2021).

A number of studies have examined the tactics employed by hotels in Bangladesh, Kenya, Ghana, Turkey, North America, and other countries to maximise room occupancy rates. Even so, no objective, scientific investigation has hitherto been conducted to determine whether or not hotels' adoption of the ideal room occupancy and revenue maximisation are significantly correlated. Notwithstanding these revelations, there is still a knowledge vacuum about how room occupancy tactics and revenue maximisation interact. This study examined the tactics used in 3-5-star hotels in particular Ghanaian regions to attain optimal room occupancy and maximise income. According to hypothesis H01, revenue maximisation in specific Ghanaian regions is not significantly correlated with the optimal room occupancy used in hotels

Methodology

The research employed a descriptive survey method to examine optimal room occupancy strategies in Ghana's hotel industry, with strategic management responses as the independent variable and revenue maximization as the dependent variable (Kothari, 2014; Creswell, 2018). The study targeted 60, 3-5 star-rated hotels, focusing on seven key areas within these establishments. A total of 496 respondents were purposively selected, including 60 general managers, 420 departmental heads, and 8 representatives each from the Ghana Tourism Authority and the Hoteliers Association of Ghana. Data collection was conducted using self-administered questionnaires for general managers and departmental heads, and interview guides for key informants from the Ghana Tourism Authority and the Hoteliers Association of Ghana. The questionnaires were pre-tested for validity and reliability (Taber, 2018). Data analysis incorporated both quantitative and qualitative methods, including factor analysis and regression analysis (Orcan, 2020). Ethical considerations were strictly followed, based on established principles (Bell and Wray-Bliss, 2009; Durkheim, 2018), with necessary approvals and consents obtained from relevant authorities. Triangulation of quantitative and qualitative data provided comprehensive insights into optimal room occupancy strategies and their impact on revenue maximization in Ghana's hotels (West and Arias, 2020).

Results and Discussion

Demographic Characteristics

The study collected data from 60 hotel managers and 420 department heads using questionnaires and conducted interviews with 16 key informants. With 487 out of 496 responses completed, the response rate was nearly 98%, reflecting participant engagement and enhancing the study's validity (Wu, 2021). The high response rate was attributed to a concise, clear questionnaire and prior briefings, ensuring representative and valid outcomes (Sharma, 2020). Pilot testing also contributed to the excellent response rate. The study aimed to understand hotel classifications for strategic responses. Table 1 shows that 75% of managers and 78% of department heads were from 3-star hotels, 20% and 17% from 4-star hotels, and 5% from 5-star hotels. The prevalence of 3-star hotels, linked to lower prices, aligns with findings by Robert (2022) and Tichaava and Kimbu (2019) on their popularity in Sub-Saharan Africa.

The study reveals a nearly equal gender distribution in managerial roles, with 65% of managers and 62% of department heads being male, and 35% and 38% female. This highlights gender gaps and the "glass ceiling" in leadership roles (Galsanjigmed & Sekiguchi, 2023; Audrey & Hansez, 2021). Women hold only 26% of senior management roles and 11% of leadership positions, revealing persistent biases (Martina & Chiara, 2020; The Castell Project, 2019). Table 1 shows the age distribution among general managers and department heads, with 54% of managers aged 45 and above, highlighting their experience. Most department heads are between 31 to 45 years old, indicating a focus on younger leaders for innovation. These dynamics blend experience with new perspectives (Asiamah, 2023). Larsson & Björklund (2021) note older managers' inclusive leadership styles. Organizations should encourage collaboration across age groups to maximize these strengths.

The study also reveals significant educational trends among managerial and departmental leaders, with most holding bachelor's degrees (61% of managers and 69% of department heads). While advanced degrees are less common, they are vital for specialization, often in technical roles. This prompts discussions on whether formal education alone ensures leadership skills, emphasizing the importance of experience and mentorship. Tailored leadership programs can bridge educational gaps, fostering diverse perspectives (Rice-Bailey & Chong, 2023; Burrell, 2023). The study examined the work experience of managers and department heads, as shown in Table 1. Results indicate that 59.1% of department heads and 41% of general managers have over 5 years of experience, which is essential for revenue optimization and strategic planning. Additionally, 91% of managers have more than 3 years in their roles, highlighting stability. These findings align with Vives et al. (2018) and Walker (2019) on the preference for experienced professionals in leadership.

Table 1 Demographic Characteristics

		Managers (%)	Departmental heads (%)
Hotel Classification	<i>3 star</i>	75.0	78.0
	<i>4 star</i>	20.0	17.0
	<i>5 star</i>	5.0	5.0
Gender distribution	<i>Male</i>	65.0	62.0
	<i>Female</i>	35.0	38.0
Age group (years)	<i>18 – 22</i>	0.0	0.97
	<i>23 – 25</i>	0.0	2.91
	<i>25 – 30</i>	3.0	12.14
	<i>31 – 35</i>	8.0	35.68
	<i>36 – 40</i>	15.0	15.53
	<i>41 – 45</i>	20.0	29.13
	<i>Above 45</i>	54.0	3.64
Highest level of education	<i>Secondary school certificate</i>	1.0	1.7
	<i>Diploma</i>	24.5	14.6
	<i>Bachelors</i>	61.0	69.9
	<i>Masters degree</i>	13.0	13.6
	<i>Doctorate degree</i>	0.5	0.2

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work Experience

<i>Less than 1 year</i>	4.0	3.2
<i>2 years</i>	5.0	3.4
<i>3 years</i>	20.0	3.9
<i>4 years</i>	30.0	23.5
<i>5 years</i>	21.0	25.8
<i>6+ years</i>	20.0	33.3

Strategies adopted to achieve optimum room occupancy during the slack period to maximize revenue

The study aimed to identify strategies used by hotels to optimize room occupancy and maximize revenue. Respondents rated various strategies, with the results summarized in Table 2. Department heads and managers in 3-5 star hotels highlighted the effectiveness of special rates for direct bookings (mean = 4.38, SD = 0.98) and market segmentation for tailored marketing (mean = 4.58, SD = 0.84). Other effective strategies included collaboration with companies (mean = 4.24, SD = 0.93), adding new product features (mean = 4.48, SD = 0.83), training staff in room-selling skills (mean = 4.42, SD = 0.98), and introducing recreational facilities (mean = 4.53, SD = 0.77). Converting one-time visitors into repeat guests (mean = 4.50, SD = 0.86) and optimizing occupancy during festivals (mean = 4.21, SD = 1.05) were also found to be beneficial. Online bookings were highly supported (mean = 4.61, SD = 0.67), aligning with Koo et al.'s (2020) findings on the revenue potential of online systems.

Recent trends emphasize direct bookings to reduce reliance on third-party agents (Nguyen et al., 2018). Price differentiation attracts price-conscious customers (Sainaghi et al., 2021), and personalized marketing enhances impact (Agag & El-Masry, 2017). Strategic alliances and continuous innovation in amenities improve guest satisfaction (Dixit et al., 2019). Effective staff training, recreational facilities, and festival-specific packages contribute to revenue growth (Wai & Ivan, 2019; Pelsmacker et al., 2018). An effective online presence drives direct bookings (Walker, 2019), and a multifaceted approach helps hotels navigate market dynamics and maximize revenue potential.

Table 2: Strategies adopted to achieve optimum room occupancy

		Departmental		Managers	
		Mean	SD	Mean	SD
1	Offer special rates or create special offers for those who book directly through your website	4.38	0.98	4.58	0.84
2	Break segments into subcategories and address them differently to optimise marketing strategy	4.10	0.80	4.63	0.71
3	Collaborate with companies to create an alliance	4.24	0.93	4.54	0.75
4	Add new product features that improve user experience	4.48	0.83	4.64	0.63
5	Take creative approaches during events to attract people and businesses opportunities to maximise revenue	4.42	0.98	4.42	0.79
6	Training employees in room selling skills	4.42	1.04	4.44	0.79

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7	Introduce recreational facilities to increase revenue	4.53	0.77	4.29	0.93
8	Turning one-time <i>visitors</i> into <i>repeat guests</i>	4.50	0.86	4.64	0.66
9	Achieving optimum occupancy during festivals to maximise revenue	4.21	1.05	4.29	0.97
10	Maximise revenue through the use of online bookings	4.61	0.67	4.66	0.66

The study findings on the use of special room rates and differentiated marketing for online room bookings were also posited by one of the key informants in an interview.

".....The hotel utilizes its website for unit promotion, and the operators take on the responsibility of directly promoting room reservations. The establishment ensures optimal room occupancy as part of its self-management strategy....." (Key informant interview [KII-001], Volta region, 2022)

A member of the Ghana Hoteliers Association provided the following insights on online room reservations.

".....Online hotel reservations provide guests with the convenience of making bookings around the clock. This is particularly advantageous for international guests, as the online booking platform utilizes automated processes, eliminating the need for manual operations. This not only streamlines the booking experience but also removes the complexity of interacting with human agents. As a result, individuals can make reservations at any time and receive prompt feedback....." (Source: [KII-002], Accra region, 2022)

The key informant interview reveals a hotel's occupancy management and advertising strategies in the Volta region. Emphasizing website room promotion reflects current digital advertising trends (Siakalli et al., 2017) and enhances the hotel's online presence (Pereira & Almeida, 2014). Promoting direct reservations demonstrates a commitment to relationship marketing, aimed at increasing guest satisfaction (Czinkota et al., 2021). These practices align with revenue management principles, which emphasize strategic pricing and demand forecasting to achieve optimal occupancy and maximize revenue (Kubickova, 2022).

Special offers to maximize occupancy

The study investigated strategies implemented by 3-5-star hotels to boost revenue. According to Figure 1, discounts (54.46%) and gift vouchers (43.26%) emerged as the predominant tactics, whereas competition-based strategies were relatively scarce (2.28%). These results corroborate Vives, Jaob, and Payeras (2018), who underscored the beneficial effects of special offers on room sales, as well as Walker (2019), who highlighted the efficacy of gift vouchers and discounts in stimulating occupancy rates.

Figure 1: Special offers to increase room occupancy

Market segmentation

Upon assessing the study, it became imperative to pinpoint the market segments utilized by the chosen hotels, underpinned by the concentrated segmentation analysis depicted in Figure 2. The findings revealed notable revelations, with 51% of the surveyed hotels focusing on corporate clientele and 41% targeting group bookings. This pattern resonates with Walker's (2019) assertion regarding the strategic significance of these segments as primary revenue drivers. The convergence between the study and Walker's viewpoint underscores the vital necessity for hotels to customize services to meet the preferences of corporate and group customers, thereby leading to heightened experiences and substantial financial benefits (Walker, 2019).

Figure 2: Market segmentation

Reasons for creating strategic alliances with other stakeholders

The study investigated the underlying motivations prompting 3-5-rated hotels in Ghana to establish strategic partnerships, illustrated in Figure 3. The analysis uncovered prominent trends, with 45% of hotels pursuing alliances to capitalize on public feedback, while 39.5% prioritized maintaining high service standards. Intriguingly, 15.2% opted for franchising as a means of expanding their market presence. These findings underscore the multifaceted roles of alliances in bolstering service quality, fostering market expansion, and aligning strategic objectives (Lopez, 2023). Such partnerships facilitate the pooling of financial and capital resources, thereby generating mutual benefits for all participating organizations.

Figure 3: Reasons for strategic alliances

Improving user experience of hotel products and services

The study explored how hotels enhance customer satisfaction with their products and services, as depicted in Figure 4. Valuable insights revealed that 47.4% of hotels relied on public feedback, 40.5% prioritized understanding user behavior, and 12.1% utilized customer advisory boards. These findings underscore the significance of user feedback in refining services, aligning with Mitchell's (2020) concept of organizational excellence. Weidenfeld (2018) stresses the importance of user feedback in continuous improvement efforts, which is consistent with the study's findings. Walker (2019) highlights the importance of understanding customer behavior for effective strategy development. Collectively, these perspectives emphasize the pivotal role of guest feedback, user behavior analysis, and strategic responsiveness in enhancing hospitality experiences.

Figure 4: Improving user experience

Other strategies for increasing room occupancy

The study investigated hotel strategies aimed at increasing room occupancy rates, unveiling pivotal tactics (Weidenfeld, 2018; Andini & Koesrindartoto, 2020). Price incentives (55.8%) are in line with prevailing industry norms. The utilization of social media (29.3%) and product samples (14.9%) underscores the growing influence of online platforms. Recreational amenities play a significant role in revenue generation (Kandampully et al., 2015). Loyalty programs and initiatives to build trust (45%) are geared towards fostering customer loyalty (Clotey et al., 2008). During peak seasons, promotions (50%) and partnerships (39%) are instrumental in boosting revenue (Xiang et al., 2015). Integration of user-friendly interfaces and cross-selling in online booking strategies has proven effective (Sigala, 2019). Customer satisfaction serves as a catalyst for revenue growth, highlighting the importance of comprehensive revenue optimization (Eklof, Podkorytova, & Malova, 2020).

Table 3: Other strategies for room occupancy

Strategy	Results	%
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1	Ways used to attract customers to hotel events		
	• Product sample distribution	74	14.9
	• Discounts	278	55.8
	• Social media	146	29.3
2	Recreational centres that generate revenue in the hotel		
	• Swimming pool	329	52.8
	• Animal Park	31	5.0
	• Gymnasium	263	42.2
3	Strategies for turning one-time customers into repeat customers		
	• Run high value promotions	66	10.2
	• Build trust with customers	291	45.0
	• Loyalty program	290	44.8
4	Strategies to increase occupancy during festivals		
	• Organize events	76	11.6
	• Tie up with local businesses	253	38.6
	• Promotions and offers	327	49.8
5	How to increase revenue through online booking		
	• Focus on customer satisfaction	107	16.7
	• Offer better booking experience than competitors	305	47.5
	• Sell the other hotel products	230	35.8

A view by a Ghana hoteliers Association respondent had this to say on other strategies to increase room occupancy.

"..... *Hotels have devised a number of strategies to attract guests. Such strategies comprises hosting events, providing platform for online booking as offering product and services promotion. These strategies has significantly increased room occupancy especially when discounts are offered to guests staying in hotels [KII-003], Bono region, 2022)*

The view by a Ghana hoteliers Association respondent collaborates this study research findings that selected hotels are adopting variety of strategies to increase optimum room occupancy to maximize revenue.

Simple Linear Regression on correlation between optimum room occupancy and maximisation of hotel revenue

A simple linear regression analysis was conducted to assess the strength of the relationship between strategies implemented to achieve optimal room occupancy and the maximization of hotel revenue. The results are presented in Table 4. The findings displayed in Table 4 reveal a strong correlation ($R = .823$, 82.3%) between the strategies employed to ensure optimal room occupancy. The R-square value indicates the proportion of the total variance in hotel revenue (the dependent variable) that can be explained by optimal room occupancy (the independent variable). The generated ANOVA yielded a p-value of less than 0.000, indicating statistical significance at the 0.05 level. This suggests that the model significantly predicts a good fit for the data. These results imply that the strategies for optimal room occupancy adopted by 3-5 star-rated hotels in selected regions of Ghana led to revenue maximization. This finding is in line with observations by SiteMinder (2021), which emphasized that

optimizing room occupancy is a key strategy for increasing revenue in hotels.

Table 4: Simple linear regression on the relationship between strategies adopted to ensure optimum room occupancy and maximisation of hotel revenue

Model	R	R Square	Adjustable R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.823 ^a	.752	.749	873.789

Conclusion

The research investigated hotel strategies aimed at increasing room occupancy and revenue during slow periods, emphasizing tactics such as providing special rates, targeting different market segments, and establishing partnerships. It highlighted the significance of introducing new features, organizing events, training staff, upgrading facilities, as well as leveraging loyal guests and online bookings. These findings are consistent with prior studies, confirming the effectiveness of these strategies in boosting revenue. The analysis emphasized the connection between these tactics and revenue maximization, emphasizing proactive steps like strategic pricing and enhancing services. However, gender disparities persisted in leadership positions, indicating ongoing systemic biases.

Recommendations

The study suggests that hotel managers prioritize collaboration with stakeholders to enhance product features and amenities, such as recreational facilities, to boost customer retention and leverage event marketing opportunities.

Suggestions for Further Research

The study indicates that factors associated with room occupancy significantly impact revenue maximization (R square = 0.899) for 3-star hotels in Ghana. However, 11.1% of the variance remains unexplained, highlighting the necessity for further research to investigate and comprehend additional factors influencing revenue optimization within this context.

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